

README

Replication file for

Carta, F. and De Philippis, M. (2023)

The forward-looking effect of increasing the full retirement age

The files from this folder allow to replicate all tables and figures of the main text and online appendices of the article “The forward-looking effect of increasing the full retirement age” by Francesca Carta and Marta De Philippis.

The code constructs the analysis file using Stata from the two data sources: the Bank of Italy’s Survey on Household Income and Wealth (SHIW) and administrative data on employees in the private non-farm sector provided by the Italian National Security Institute (INPS). Two main files run all of the code to generate the data for the 15 figures and 14 tables in the paper (including those reported in the appendices). The replicator should expect the code to run for about 7 minutes (4 on SHIW data, 3 on INPS data).

The code was written for Stata 17, and executed on Intel i5-8365U CPU with 24.0 GB RAM using Windows 16. Total computation time to run all do-files as for SHIW data on January 17, 2023 was 4 minutes; 3 minutes as for INPS administrative data.

Data Availability and Provenance Statements

The SHIW is a biannual survey administered by the Bank of Italy to a representative sample of Italian households and is the main source of information about family income and wealth in Italy. We use seven waves ranging from 2004 to 2016 (Bank of Italy, 2004, 2006, 2008, 2010, 2012, 2015, 2018). The sample comprises approximately 8,000 households (20,000 individuals) per year.

Data are publicly available and can be freely downloaded from the Bank of Italy’s website ([Banca d'Italia - Distribuzione dei microdati \(bancaditalia.it\)](https://www.bancaitalia.it)). Documentation is available at [Banca d'Italia - Documentazione per l'utilizzo dei microdati \(bancaditalia.it\)](https://www.bancaitalia.it). Downloading the relevant files takes approximately 5 minutes.

All the documentation and raw data are also provided in the replication package. To explore the main mechanisms driving the effect uncovered in the paper, the authors gathered additional data. First, they used data on regional vacancy rates that have been provided by Italian National Statistical Institute (Istat) stat upon request ([here](#)) and cannot be distributed (lambda.dta). Second, the authors use data on regional unemployment rates (disoccupazione.xls) that can be downloaded from the Istat data warehouse on labour market indicators ([here](#)).

In subsection 5.4 (Table 5; Appendix B and Figure C3 and Table C4) the paper uses confidential microdata from the Italian National Social Security Institute (INPS) provided to the Bank of Italy on the basis of a specific agreement. In particular, as described in the paper, we use a random and representative 6.5% sample of the population (i.e., individuals born in 24 randomly picked birth

dates every year). We combine several datasets provided by INPS: (i) the complete contributory histories of individuals who worked as employees in the private nonfarm sector for at least one period in their life between 1990 and 2016; (ii) the annual employer-employee matched database, which contains the information on each job spell between 2005 and 2016 and (iii) the list of pension recipients, to recover whether these individuals receive a public pension. Researchers interested in access to the data may contact INPS representatives at dcstudiericerche@inps.it. Accessing these data usually requires to apply for the [VisitINPS scholars project](#).

Statement about Rights

The authors of the manuscript have legitimate access to and permission to use the data contained within this replication package.

Summary of Availability

Some data **cannot be made** publicly available.

Computational requirements

Software Requirements

- Stata (code was last run with version 17)
 - esttab
 - reghdfe
 - distinct
 - tuples
 - ftools

Memory and Runtime Requirements

Approximate time needed to reproduce the analyses on a standard (CURRENT YEAR) desktop machine: <10 minutes, 4 for the analysis on SHIW data (1 minute for the code building the dataset, 3 minutes the one carrying out the analysis), 3 minutes for the analysis on INPS data.

Details

The code was last run on a **Intel i5-8365U CPU with 24.0 GB RAM** using **Windows 16**.

Instructions to Replicators

Description of the replication package

This archive is structured in three folders:

- /documents: it contains SHIW questionnaires and variables description.
- /raw data: it contains the yearly raw data as they are downloaded from the Bank of Italy's website in ASCII format. The survey is biannual and data from 2004 to 2016 are used.

- /replication
 - /data: it contains stata raw datasets for each year of SHIW. dataset_all.dta is the main dataset used in the SHIW analysis. This dataset is created by the dofile dataset.do in /replication/pgm. Then it is merged with lambda.dta (not publicly provided) and with disoccupazione.xls (provided in the replication package).
 - /graphs: it contains the figures produced with main_revEJ.do using the SHIW and INPS data
 - /pgm: it contains the dofiles necessary to run the analysis with the SHIW and INPS data
 - /tables: it contains the tables produced with main_revEJ.do using the SHIW and INPS data

Description of the codes and main instructions

- Edit pgm/dataset.do to adjust the default path (line 2). This is the code that builds the SHIW dataset for the analysis. It produces dataset_all.dta.
- Edit pgm/main_revEJ.do to adjust the default path (lines 4, 6, 8, 10, 12, 14). This is the main dofile for the SHIW analysis. To run it, you need to request regional data on vacancy rates (line 213) to the Italian National Statistical Institute (Istat), as specified above, and use Istat data on unemployment rates (line 245; the dataset is in the folder /replication/data). The dofile main_revEJ.do runs other dofiles (descriptives.do, regressions_fl.do, heterogeneityall.do, regressions_nonlinear.do, regressions_rob_cyclical.do, regressions_youngcontrol.do, regressions_direct.do, figures_shock.do) that produce the tables and figures of the paper (saved respectively in /tables and /graphs; see the Table below for a more detailed description).
- Edit pgm/main_INPS_revEJ.do to adjust the default path (lines 2, 3 and 6). This is the main dofile for the INPS analysis. It generates all tables and figures as described in the Table below.

List of tables, figures and programs

Figure/Table #	Program	Line Number	Output file
Table 1	n.a. (no data)		
Table 2	descriptives.do	56, 97, 101	des_paper_ind.tex, des_paper_part_hhwife.tex, des_paper_part_hhhusb.tex

Table 3	regressions_fl.do	101-113	individualms_fem_active2.tex, individualms_fem_employed2.tex, individualms_fem_unemployed2.tex, individualms_men_active2.tex, individualms_men_employed2.tex, individualms_men_unemployed2.tex
Table 4	heterogeneityall.do	56, 110	individual_active_het.tex, individual_active_riccoedu.tex
Table 5	main_INPS_revEJ	170-184	fem5559_inps.tex, fem4554_inps.tex, men5559_inps.tex, men4554_inps.tex
Table 6	regressions_fl.do	116-129	individualms_cross_activehusb.tex, individualms_cross_pensionatohusb.tex
Table 7	regressions_fl.do	101-113	individualms_fem_wage_gross_fami2.tex, individualms_fem_reddito_fami2.tex, individualms_fem_welfare_fami2.tex, individualms_fem_savings_fami2
Table A1	n.a. (no data)		
Table A2	regressions_nonlinear.do	76-86	individualms_fem_active3nl.tex, individualms_fem_employed3nl.tex, individualms_fem_unemployed3nl.tex, individualms_men_active3nl.tex, individualms_men_employed3nl.tex, individualms_men_unemployed3nl.tex
Table A3	regressions_rob_cyclical.do	6-38	individualms_fem_active_UR.tex, individualms_fem_employed_UR.tex, individualms_fem_unemployed_UR.tex
Table A4	regressions_youngcontrol.do	16-42	individualms_activeold.tex, individualms_unemployedold.tex, individualms_employedold.tex
Table A5	regressions_fl.do	116-129	individualms_cross_activewife.tex, individualms_cross_pensionatowife.tex
Table B1	main_INPS_revEJ.do	71	des_paper_inps.tex
Table C1	regressions_direct.do	15 and 28	des_paper_directtreatedcol_12, des_paper_directtreatedcol_34
Table C2	regressions_direct.do	119	individual_active_mechmarried.tex, individual_employed_mechmarried.tex, individual_active_mechcross, individual_employed_mechcross
Table C3	main_INPS_revEJ.do	349	individual_employed2_mechinps.tex
Figure 1	n.a. (no data)		

Figure 2	figures_shock.do	27	figure2.pdf
Figure 3	figures_shock.do	41	figure3.pdf
Figure 4	figures_shock.do	70	figure4.pdf
Figure 5	regressions_fl.do	200	figure5.pdf
Figure 6	regressions_fl.do	236	figure6.pdf
Figure A1	figures_shock.do	104	figureA1.pdf
Figure A2	regressions_youngcontrol.d o	126	figureA2.pdf
Figure A3	regressions_fl.do	270	figureA3.pdf
Figure B1	main_INPS_revEJ.do	97-125	figureB1.pdf
Figure B2	main_INPS_revEJ.do	74-90	figureB2.pdf
Figure B3	main_INPS_revEJ.do	190-290	figureB3.pdf
Figure C1	regressions_direct.do	169, 212	figureC1a.pdf, figureC1b.pdf
Figure C2	regressions_direct.do	276	figureC2.pdf
Figure C3	regressions_direct.do	320	figureC3.pdf
Figure C4	main_INPS_revEJ.do	299-312	figureC4.pdf

References

Bank of Italy (2004). 'Survey on household income and wealth - 2004', Annual archive version 4-3-2004, available at <https://www.bancaditalia.it/statistiche/tematiche/indagini-famiglie-impres/bilanci-famiglie/distribuzione-microdati/index.html?page=3>

Bank of Italy (2006). 'Survey on household income and wealth - 2006', Annual archive version 10-2-2006, available at <https://www.bancaditalia.it/statistiche/tematiche/indagini-famiglie-impres/bilanci-famiglie/distribuzione-microdati/index.html?page=3>

Bank of Italy (2008). 'Survey on household income and wealth - 2008', Annual archive version 8-2-2008 available at <https://www.bancaditalia.it/statistiche/tematiche/indagini-famiglie-impres/bilanci-famiglie/distribuzione-microdati/index.html?page=3>

Bank of Italy (2010). 'Survey on household income and wealth - 2010', Annual archive version 8-1-2010 available at <https://www.bancaditalia.it/statistiche/tematiche/indagini-famiglie-impres/bilanci-famiglie/distribuzione-microdati/index.html?page=2>

Bank of Italy (2012). 'Survey on household income and wealth - 2012', Annual archive version 6-1-2012 available at <https://www.bancaditalia.it/statistiche/tematiche/indagini-famiglie-impres/bilanci-famiglie/distribuzione-microdati/index.html?page=2>

Bank of Italy (2015). 'Survey on household income and wealth - 2014', Annual archive version 3-12-2015 available at <https://www.bancaditalia.it/statistiche/tematiche/indagini-famiglie-impres/bilanci-famiglie/distribuzione-microdati/index.html?page=2>

Bank of Italy (2018). 'Survey on household income and wealth - 2016', Annual archive version 12-03-2018 <https://www.bancaditalia.it/statistiche/tematiche/indagini-famiglie-impres/bilanci-famiglie/distribuzione-microdati/index.html?page=1>

Italian Social Security Institute (2019). 'Individual level careers - Random sample', Annual archive version 2019.